

IMPROVING PROMISING METHODS FOR MANAGING THE ACTIVITIES OF INSPECTORS ON WOMEN'S ISSUES

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific analysis of the management of inspectors' activities on women's issues in developed countries. Based on the data, we will consider the role and activities of inspectors in society by analyzing inter-institutional cooperation, state policy and the role of public organizations. The article provides practical suggestions that can help increase the effectiveness of inspectors on women's issues in our country. The experience of developed countries, including methods, standards and strategic approaches, is covered, as well as discussions on the study of best practices in the field of gender equality and women's rights protection. The research results in the article serve as an important source for use in creating effective strategies for optimizing the activities of inspectors on women's issues.

Keywords: women's issues, the activities of inspectors in developed countries, scientific analysis of gender equality, the activities of inspectors, their tasks, responsibilities, legal status, the importance of cooperation between state and public organizations, increasing citizen participation and gender equality, social stability of society.

PRAVOVOYE POLOJENIYE JENSHIN I DEVUSHEK, VOPROSI INSPEKTOROV I OSNOVI UPRAVLENIYA IX DEYATELNOSTYU

Abstract: V dannoy statye providotsya nauchniy analiz upravleniya deyatelnostyu inspektorov po delam jenshin v razvitix stranax. Na osnove poluchennih dannix mi rassmatrivayem rol i deyatelnost inspektorov v obshestve, analiziruya rol mejvedomstvennogo sotrudnichestva, gosudarstvennoy politiki i obshestvennih organizatsii. In the article, there are practical examples that can improve the efficiency of inspectors' work. Osveshayetsya opit razvitix stran, vklyuchaya discussii o metodax, standartax i strategicheskix podkhodax, v chastnosti, ob izuchenii peredovogo opita v oblasti gendernogo ravenstva i zashiti prav genshin. The results of research and the use of valuable resources for the purpose of creating effective strategic optimization of inspectors and women's issues.

Keywords: deyatelnost inspektorov, ix obyazannosti, otvetstvennost, pravovoy status, vajnost sotrudnichestva gosudarstvennih i obshestvennih organizatsiy, povisheniye aktiviyi grajdan i gendernogo ravenstva, sotsialnaya stabilitat obshestva.

LEGAL STATUS OF WOMEN AND GIRLS ISSUES INSPECTORS AND ESSENTIALS OF MANAGEMENT OF THEIR ACTIVITIES

Abstract: This article analyzes the legal status of women's inspectors and the essence of managing their activities. Inspectors play an important role in protecting women's rights, ensuring gender equality and combating violence. The article examines their legal status, duties and responsibilities, as well as mechanisms necessary to manage their activities.

Factors such as governance, monitoring, community engagement, and resource provision are important in improving the effectiveness of inspectors.

Keywords: activities of inspectors, their duties, responsibilities, legal status, importance of cooperation between state and public organizations, increasing citizen participation and gender equality, social stability of society.

ENTRANCE

The rapid development of cities around the world and their increasingly modern appearance require the provision of public order and safety in their central streets and other public places in line with the requirements of the times. According to statistics, in 2019, the share of street crimes in total crimes in most developed countries was on average 20.1%, and the figure is growing every year, and in Russia alone, in 2019, an average of 34.1% of crimes such as murder, assault, rape, robbery, theft, and hooliganism were committed in public places. It is important to note that among these figures, there are many cases involving women. Scientific research is being carried out around the world to study the problems of improving the management of the police network dealing with women's crime. Particularly important are issues such as creating effective mechanisms for inspectors to provide services to the population and cooperate with the general public, increasing their work efficiency by providing them with new generation technologies and software systems, and organizing their service activities based on purposeful models (modeling).

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Ensuring the security of citizens is one of the important issues in all countries, and the management of structural units engaged in this task is carried out through various ways and methods. Each country has its own experience in this area, and their study and implementation in the system of ensuring public order and security in our country is one of the urgent issues today. As the legal scholar DV Vasilyev noted, the study of foreign experience allows us to determine important directions for the development of society, to prevent the repetition of mistakes and erroneous approaches in the process of the long historical development of mankind. In addition, as NG Khiznyakov rightly noted, when carefully studying and implementing the experience of foreign countries, it is necessary to take into account the specific characteristics of each country.

Some aspects of the management of the activities of inspectors of internal affairs bodies and women's issues have been studied to a certain extent in scientific research conducted by legal scholars of our country. In particular, issues related to the management of internal affairs bodies have been studied by legal scholars such as HR Alimov, BE Qosimov, O'.Kh. Mukhamedov, I. Ismailov, HT Odilqoriyev, YS Pulatov, ZR Ro'ziyev, UT Tadzhikhanov, AS Tursunov, IA Khamedov, OT Khusanov.

Directly, some issues related to the organizational and legal framework for managing the activities of inspectors on women's issues, cooperation with other entities (I. Ismailov, MZ Ziyodullayev), participation in the prevention of offenses and crime prevention (JS Mukhtorov), their role in ensuring the control and licensing system (SM Selimanova), some aspects of cooperation with citizens' self-government bodies (ZR Ro'ziyev), and participation in the prevention of offenses among unorganized youth (S.R. Gofurov) were studied.

RESULTS

The results of the study are as follows: A number of scholars argue that the organizational structure, functions, and distribution of powers between different levels of

foreign police agencies depend on the forms of governance and the degree of centralization of the state that exist in each country.

Since the inception of modern law enforcement, patrolling has been a primary means of crime prevention. By the 1970s, research into improving patrolling had begun to gain momentum. As a result, patrolling has become more effective, especially in Western countries, both in terms of quality and quantity. Furthermore, researchers studying the police systems of Western countries have found that although police services in these countries are provided by a variety of professional organizations, including community police forces, private security agencies, the armed forces, and government agencies with various supervisory and investigative powers, the most prominent of these agencies is the community police force, which patrols public areas on foot and in vehicles. They are the most visible representatives of civil authority and usually represent models associated with police organizations. Russian scientist AN Badmaev also emphasizes that great attention is paid to the organization and strengthening of patrol service abroad and, as a rule, it is manifested in law enforcement agencies as a basic, independent and very numerous structure. This requires a systematic approach to studying the experience gained by foreign countries in managing the activities of inspectors of internal affairs bodies on women's issues in order to effectively implement it in our national legislation and practice of its application. Therefore, in order to achieve the intended goal, it is advisable to study the foreign experience in managing the activities of inspectors of internal affairs bodies on women's issues in a systematized manner as follows.

DISCUSSION

Inspectors of internal affairs bodies for women's issues make up 60 percent of the national police force and are subordinate to the city police during their service. Great importance is attached to the development and improvement of the organization of patrol services in the country. Researcher TI Marayev, who studied the role of French police forces in ensuring public order and security during mass events, emphasizes that the patrol-post service occupies a leading position compared to other bodies in the process of preparing for and holding mass events at all levels in the country.

In Italy, which has another unique experience in the field of ensuring public order and security, and combating crime, the police is also a highly centralized system. Currently, there are three law enforcement agencies in Italy that perform police functions. All of them have different organizational structures and subordination. These are: 1) the State Police (Polizia di Stato), founded in 1852, also known as the Public Security Police (Forze di pubblica sicurezza); 2) the Carabinieri Corps (Arma (Corpo) dei carabinieri), founded in 1814 on the model of the French gendarmerie; 3) the Financial Guard Corps (Corpo della Guardia), founded in 1907 in addition to the Carabinieri.

Although tasks in the field of public order and security are carried out by several independent, non-subordinate police organizations with special legal status, the State Police coordinates their activities.

In addition to the above systems, in Italy there are also municipal police (Corpo di polizia locale) established in cities with more than 10 thousand inhabitants, which are not part of the state police system and are financed by the budget of the authorities and are subordinate to the relevant city municipality. This type of police, which is carried out in the city, is a reserve of the State Police for operational-investigative and other activities. Its main task is to maintain public order in the territory, monitor the sanitary condition of settlements

and ensure road safety. This service is carried out on foot, in police cars and motorcycles. In some cities they also use service dogs and horses.

CONCLUSION

The elimination of crime among women is an urgent issue in any country and any society. Inspectors of internal affairs bodies for women's issues are a component of the management of the IIO system. Through them, the IIO enters into organizational and legal relations with state administrative bodies, public associations and citizens.

It constitutes a system of state authorities that ensure public order and security, coordinate relations in this area on the basis of law and order and a unified state policy, and protect society and legal norms. Inspectors of internal affairs bodies for women's issues occupy a special place in this system.

A detailed study of the activities of inspectors of internal affairs bodies on women's issues requires, first of all, to clarify the content of the concepts of "public order" and "public safety", realizing that this is a major step towards eliminating the crime among women that forms its basis and thereby ensuring the peace of the entire society. Because without understanding the essence of these concepts, it is impossible to understand the content and essence of the activities of inspectors of internal affairs bodies on women's issues.

Their activities are supported by legal frameworks, clear tasks and responsibilities, which helps to increase their effectiveness.

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